

Measuring Regional Attractiveness in Europe Through Regional Mobility Patterns Using Big Data

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Abstract. This study quantifies regional attractiveness in Europe using realized mobility flows from seven distinct mobility types. Departing from traditional potential-based metrics, we compute net migration across NUTS2 regions through two different approaches. Results consistently highlight urban centres as highly attractive and revealing regional exceptions, notably in Nordic areas where non-permanent mobility forms prevail. Our findings underscore the need to integrate mobility data with conventional indicators to more accurately evaluate regional attractiveness and inform policy.

Keywords. Regional Attractiveness, Mobility Patterns, Regional Characteristics

1. Introduction

Regional attractiveness is a fundamental driver of spatial mobility, influencing economic growth, labor markets, and population distributions across Europe. Traditionally, attractiveness has been assessed using static indicators such as GDP per capita, infrastructure quality, or social amenities (Buch et al., 2017; Silvanto & Ryan, 2018). However, these measures focus on potential attractiveness, estimating the desirability of a region based on its characteristics, rather than capturing the actual observed attractiveness of regions. In contrast, our study introduces a realized measure of regional attractiveness by analyzing observed mobility flows. Rather than relying on assumptions about which regions has the potential to be attractive, we quantify where people move as proxy to actual attractiveness of the regions, offering a more behaviorally grounded approach.

Moreover, unlike prior studies that primarily focus on permanent migration (Balaz et al., 2004; Cameron et al., 2005), we incorporate seven distinct types of mobility: permanent migration, long-term student mobility, short-

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term student mobility, seasonal work, long-distance commuting, cross-border commuting, and multilocal living. Each type reflects different dimensions of attractiveness, capturing both long-term settlement decisions and temporary, circular, or work-related mobility (Barrioluengo & Flisi, 2017; Järv et al., 2023; Lehtonen et al., 2015; Lundmark, 2006). By considering these diverse mobility types, our approach provides a more nuanced view of regional attractiveness that moves beyond traditional, static measures.

2. Methods

To quantify regional attractiveness, we analyze net migration patterns across European NUTS2 regions (Eurostat, 2003). We extracted mobility patterns using multiple data sources (Figure 1): Labour Force Survey (LFS), Erasmus student mobility data, and Twitter-derived mobility data (Väisänen et al., 2024a). Net migration for each mobility type is then calculated as the difference between inflows and outflows. We employ two approaches to derive a regional attractiveness index. First, we compute the average normalized net migration for each region, providing a straightforward measure based on aggregate flows. Second, we apply Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to the standardized net migration variables, extracting dominant patterns in the data to generate a composite attractiveness index. This dual-method approach ensures robustness and allows validation against existing attractiveness indicators (Silvanto & Ryan, 2018). By comparing the two approaches, we assess whether a simple aggregation or a more complex dimensionality reduction technique provides better insight into regional mobility dynamics.

Figure 1. Examples of mobility flows in Europe (total movement from 2012 to 2022): (a) permanent migration and (b) long-term student mobility. Edge bundling is applied to enhance visualization (Väisänen et al., 2024b).

3. Results

Both approaches yield highly similar results, with minor differences observed primarily in Nordic countries and Baltic region (Figure 2). Urban centers and regions with high population density consistently exhibit high levels of attractiveness, reinforcing the idea that economic opportunities, accessibility, and infrastructure are key drivers of mobility. An interesting exception is found in the Nordic countries, where northern regions show a high level of attractiveness despite their lower population density. This is likely due to the prevalence of multilocal living arrangements and seasonal work, particularly in industries such as tourism and resource extraction. Regions with lower levels of attractiveness are predominantly found in less densely populated areas and regions that do not contain national capitals. This contrast is particularly pronounced in countries such as Germany, France, Hungary, and Poland, where major metropolitan areas attract significant net inflows, while peripheral and rural regions experience consistent outflows.

Figure 2. Comparison of regional attractiveness in Europe using (a) the average net migration approach and (b) the PCA-based approach. Darker shades indicate higher attractiveness.

4. Discussion

Our findings emphasize the necessity of going beyond potential-based measures of attractiveness and incorporating realized mobility patterns to better understand how regions actually function as mobility hubs. While potential-based indices, built on regional characteristics such as economic strength, legal and regulatory aspects, and quality of life (Silvanto & Ryan, 2018), are useful for assessing a region's capacity to attract people, they do not necessarily reflect real mobility flows. Realized mobility data, as presented in our approach, provides an empirically grounded measure of attractiveness, based on actual movement patterns rather than assumed desirability.

For policymakers, relying solely on potential attractiveness can be misleading when evaluating regional development strategies. Potential attractiveness can help set long-term goals and identify structural advantages or weaknesses, but to assess the effectiveness of policies and understand real mobility trends, realized attractiveness must be taken into account. This study provides a framework for doing so by incorporating seven distinct mobility types. Policymakers should not limit their assessments to permanent migration alone, as different mobility forms contribute uniquely to regional development.

The results show that some regions with high potential attractiveness fail to translate that into strong realized attractiveness, suggesting barriers that prevent people from moving there. At the same time, certain regions with lower potential attractiveness indicators exhibit strong realized mobility flows (e.g., Nordic countries), demonstrating that factors beyond traditional economic measures contribute to a region's ability to attract people. By considering a more comprehensive set of mobility patterns, our approach helps policymakers move beyond static measures and assess the actual impact of regional policies on mobility flows.

In summary, our findings support the argument that potential-based and realized attractiveness measures should be used together for a more complete picture of regional dynamics. While potential attractiveness is important for long-term strategic planning, realized attractiveness provides direct, behaviorally driven evidence of where people actually move. Policymakers seeking to evaluate their region's success in attracting and retaining people need to integrate both approaches into their assessments, ensuring that strategies align not just with theoretical potential, but with actual mobility trends.

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